

AI and Digital Authoritarianism in MENA

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Over the past two decades, regimes across the MENA region have invested in technologies that have made surveillance cheaper, censorship more granular, and propaganda more scalable (Freedom House 2023). Rapid advances in AI technologies have accelerated the speed, scale, and integration of these capabilities (Feldstein 2023). Governments increasingly combine biometric identification, “smart city” sensor networks, social media platform monitoring, and influence operations into mutually reinforcing systems. Regimes are adopting AI as a strategic infrastructure that reshapes how threats are anticipated, how publics are managed, and how information is controlled (Beidollahkhani 2025).

The same technologies that strengthen state control, however, can also strengthen civic resilience. Activists, journalists, and civil society organizations can also use AI for translation, documentation, verification, and rapid counter-messaging (Espiritusanto et al. 2024). Below, I describe how AI technologies are bolstering the digital authoritarian toolkit in the MENA region and then highlight how they simultaneously offer new opportunities for opposition and low-resource actors to achieve their goals.

Surveillance

AI technologies have facilitated a shift from surveillance of known dissidents toward population-scale monitoring by automating identification, combining disparate data sources, and turning infrastructure into searchable, real-time governance tools (Kalluri 2025; Brookings 2021; Reuters 2023; Fontes 2022). When citizens believe the state can recognize them quickly and cheaply, self-censorship and political caution diffuse far beyond those who are directly repressed (Zhuravskaya, Petrova, and Enikolopov 2020).

For example, Iran has leveraged AI-enhanced technologies for hijab enforcement. These technologies have enabled the regime to more systematically use facial recognition and road-camera networks for detecting and identifying alleged hijab violations, alongside a citizen-reporting app (Nazer) that can be used to trigger police action (Associated Press 2025; Council on Foreign Relations 2025). This combination of networked cameras and biometric identification reduces the marginal cost of sanctioning ordinary citizens—especially when paired with automatable administrative penalties such as fines and vehicle seizures, rather than formal

prosecutions. Computer-vision systems can flag potential violations from drone or CCTV footage, facial recognition can attach a name or identity token, and app-based reports can route incidents into an automated enforcement pipeline.

Similarly, Egypt's New Administrative Capital, a large, centrally planned city built east of Cairo, shows how "smart city" governance can embed surveillance into the built environment. The city includes more than 6,000 CCTV cameras and a centralized command setup. Although it has been marketed as advancing security and efficiency, digital rights advocates have warned that such infrastructure can facilitate monitoring and suppression of dissent in an authoritarian context (Reuters 2023). In an AI-enhanced smart city, cameras become queryable sensors. Computer vision and centralized analytics make it possible to search across time and space at a previously impossible speed and scale. Once sensor networks and centralized analytics are in place, the marginal cost of repurposing them for political surveillance is low. Smart city framing also offers plausible deniability, allowing regimes to present pervasive monitoring as a neutral modernization project.

Regimes have also increasingly integrated AI analytics into policing through "smart policing" platforms. The Abu Dhabi Police have partnered with Presight, an Abu Dhabi-based AI and big data analytics company, to integrate an "AI-Policing Suite" into police operations (Tech & Justice Project n.d.). Presight's marketing materials highlight geospatial insights and "predictive analytics" to support proactive measures (Presight n.d.). Rather than responding to crimes, predictive policing tools can be used to preempt gatherings, disrupt networks, or prevent "risk," particularly in states where broad security laws and

speech restrictions define dissent as a threat to public order. These predictive and adaptive AI systems can turn surveillance into anticipatory governance, shaping political behavior before overt contestation occurs (Beidollahkhani 2025).

This population-scale monitoring is frequently complemented by high-resolution targeting of key individuals through spyware and device compromise. For example, Gulf regimes increasingly use a combination of spyware, facial recognition, and mass surveillance tools (European Council on Foreign Relations 2022). Pegasus spyware, which is produced and exported by Israel, has been used to hack multiple Bahraini and Saudi activists (Citizen Lab 2021). Pegasus has additionally been used to hack journalists at Al Jazeera and Al Araby TV via iMessage (Citizen Lab 2020). In North Africa, Amnesty International reported repeated Pegasus targeting of Moroccan journalist Omar Radi (Amnesty International 2020). Such spyware captures communications, contacts, and location histories that can be triaged and operationalized via automated analytics and network mapping.

Censorship

Censorship in MENA has historically been quite blunt—blocking platforms or shutting down networks. But AI tools have increasingly allowed regimes to use selective censorship that targets specific sites, services, or content types while preserving enough connectivity for commerce and state capacity. AI-enhanced censorship typically operates through ISP-level infrastructure, including deep packet inspection (the examination of internet traffic in transit); filtering (the restriction of access to specific content); and automated classification (the use of software to identify

and sort traffic or content), all of which enable selective blocking. Humans still set the censorship rules, but AI helps detect patterns in internet traffic and classify content or services for enforcement. Meanwhile, automation enables those blocking decisions to be carried out quickly and at scale.

Iran is often cited as a leading example of selective, “smart” censorship. The regime has long pursued “intelligent filtering” that can restrict specific sites, pages, features, or content categories while preserving enough connectivity for commerce and routine governance (Reuters 2024). AI tools have been used for classification and traffic identification, which makes it possible to automatically sort and act on traffic or content types at scale (ARTICLE 19 2026). This infrastructure makes censorship more flexible as restrictions can be tightened selectively during moments of contention without imposing the high economic and administrative costs of a full internet blackout (ARTICLE 19 2026). Notably, however, the regime has repeatedly resorted to Internet shutdowns during high-threat unrest—suggesting that smart filtering is perhaps used for routine governance while shutdowns remain the regime’s crisis tool (Reuters 2024; Access Now 2023; NetBlocks 2022; NetBlocks 2026).

In the Gulf, AI-enabled censorship often operates through platform-wide monitoring and automated content moderation on social media. Security services can use AI to scan large-scale social media data, flagging politically sensitive content, mapping networks, and prioritizing accounts for reporting, takedown requests, or offline questioning (Freedom House 2019; Freedom House 2023). In Bahrain, for example, authorities reportedly forced a user to remove an Instagram post about protests against normalization with

Israel and have also exploited platform reporting mechanisms to target activists and independent journalists. In Saudi Arabia, authorities have requested that platforms such as Netflix and YouTube remove content deemed “inappropriate,” while in the UAE, pervasive surveillance of online activists and journalists has contributed to extensive self-censorship. At the same time, platforms’ own AI-driven moderation tools can amplify state pressure. Because enforcement is opaque and frequently automated, content removal and account restrictions may occur preemptively around well-known “red lines,” producing censorship effects even when formal requests are not visible (ECDHR 2026; MEI 2021). Importantly, however, Gulf regimes do not control the dominant social media platforms themselves. Because major services are largely U.S.-based, governments in MENA typically lack direct, state-run tools for platform-level censorship and instead rely more on monitoring, pressure, and takedown requests routed through platform governance systems.

Propaganda

AI tools make propaganda and influence campaigns easier to run because a small team can produce and translate large amounts of content quickly and cheaply. They also make narratives more convincing by enabling high-volume, stylistically diverse, rapidly iterated messaging (Marcellino et al. 2023). Social media platform disclosures offer documentation of organized manipulation tied to regional actors. Meta has reported removing coordinated inauthentic behavior networks originating in the UAE and Egypt, as well as a separate operation in Saudi Arabia involving clusters of accounts and pages designed to mislead audiences (Meta 2019). Generative AI accelerates these operations by lowering

the production and iteration costs of persuasive content. Generative AI reduces time, money, and skill barriers for producing disinformation and propaganda, potentially overwhelming detection and moderation systems (Feldstein 2023). For example, Google’s Threat Analysis Group reports that it has terminated Iran-linked influence operations that pushed automated pro-regime Arabic-language narratives (Google Threat Analysis Group 2024).

Gulf states are increasingly investing in “sovereign” generative AI by developing or backing domestic Arabic large language models (LLMs). The UAE’s government-linked Technology Innovation Institute developed the open-weight Falcon series (Almazrouei et al. 2023), and the Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence released Jais, an Arabic-centric foundation model (Sengupta et al. 2023). The Saudi Data and AI Authority (SDAIA) has developed ALLaM, an Arabic-English LLM (Bari et al. 2024). These projects may allow states to influence what content LLMs will generate, refuse, or systematically omit on sensitive topics. As everyday citizens increasingly turn to LLMs for information, the ability to manipulate the content they produce offers regimes a new lever of information control.

Civic Resilience

Many of the same features of AI technologies that enable digital authoritarianism—automation, translation, classification, and summarization—can also strengthen civic resilience by making documentation, verification, coordination, and public outreach faster for low-resource actors (Espiritusanto, Nachawati-Rego, and Magallón-Rosa 2024; Kerley, Miller, and Campagnucci 2024). For example, before the fall of the Assad regime, the Syrian

Archive and Mnemonic ecosystem use automated collection and structured verification workflows to preserve open-source evidence for advocacy and accountability, even when platform moderation or deletions remove content (Syrian Archive n.d.; Mnemonic 2020; Exposing the Invisible 2021).

AI can also support circumvention of censorship and continuity of Internet access by helping communities quickly diagnose blocks, share workable configurations in local language, and adapt when censors change tactics. During Iran’s 2022 protests, some people were still able to communicate and access news despite state blocking by using digital circumvention tools like Psiphon and Tor Snowflake, which allow users to access blocked online content by routing traffic through external networks. Even when these workarounds only worked for some users or for limited periods, they show a basic form of resilience under digital authoritarianism. Activists and ordinary citizens tested what still worked, adapted quickly when blocks changed, and shared step-by-step guidance so others could stay connected (OONI 2022; OONI n.d.).

AI can also strengthen a different kind of resilience by helping civil society respond faster to state-aligned propaganda and information control. For example, in Turkey, protesters have leveraged AI to maintain anonymity and create viral anti-regime content (Gümrükçü 2025). The Arab Fact-Checkers Network’s partnership with Full Fact (a UK-based independent fact-checking non-profit) aims to build AI tools that speed up verification in Arabic, and JournalismAI supported an AI-powered WhatsApp bot designed to deliver quicker fact-checks for MENA audiences. These tools help opposition contest official narratives and reduce the effectiveness of

disinformation by making rapid, credible corrections easier to produce and distribute (AFCN 2024; JournalismAI 2024).

As AI tools continue to advance, digital politics in MENA—and around the globe—will likely remain a race of adaptation. Governments will keep integrating AI into surveillance, censorship, and influence operations to monitor the public and manage information more efficiently, while activists, journalists, and civil society will use many of the same capabilities to document abuse, maintain access, verify claims, and coordinate responses. ♦

References

Almazrouei, Ebtesam, et al. 2023. “The Falcon Series of Open Language Models.” *arXiv* (2311.16867). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.16867>

Amnesty International. 2020. “NSO Group spyware used to target Moroccan journalist Omar Radi.” June 22. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2020/06/nso-spyware-used-against-moroccan-journalist/>

Arab Fact-Checkers Network (AFCN). 2024. “AFCN and Full Fact Unite for AI-Powered Fact-Checking in Arabic.” April 2. <https://arabfcn.net/en/blog/2024/04/02/afcncn-and-full-fact-unite-for-ai-powered-fact-checking-in-arabic/>

ARTICLE 19. 2026. *Tightening the Net: China’s Infrastructure of Oppression in Iran*. London: ARTICLE 19.

Aspen, Eliza and Spandana Singh. 2021. “Content Moderation Trends in the MENA Region: Censorship, Discrimination by Design, and Linguistic Challenges.” *Middle East Institute* (MEI). August 25. <https://mei.edu/publication/content-moderation-trends-mena-region-censorship-discrimination-design-and-linguistic/>

Bari, M. Saiful, et al. 2024. “ALLaM: Large Language Models for Arabic and English.” *arXiv* (2407.15390). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.15390>

Beidollahkhani, Arash. 2025. “From Predicting Dissent to Programming Power: Analyzing AI-Driven Authoritarian Governance in the Middle East through TRIAD Framework.” *Democratization*, 1-24. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13510347.2025.2576527>

ECDHR. 2026. “Platform Compliance in the Middle East: How Opaque Content Moderation Enables Quiet Authoritarian Censorship.” January 21.

Espiritusanto, Óscar, Leila Nachawati-Rego, and Raúl Magallón-Rosa. 2024. “The Role of AI in Citizen Journalism, Human Rights Activism, and Monitoring: Limits and Possibilities.” In *Journalism, Digital Media and the Fourth Industrial Revolution*, eds. José Sixto-García, Alberto Quian, Ana-Isabel Rodríguez-Vázquez, Alba Silva-Rodríguez, Xosé Soengas-Pérez, 211-226. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-63153-5_16

Evdokimov, Leonid, Maria Xynou, Mohammad El-Taher, Hassan Al-Azhary, and Sarah Mohsen. 2018. *The State of Internet Censorship in Egypt*. OONI + AFTE. July 2. <https://ooni.org/post/egypt-internet-censorship/>

Feldstein, Steven. 2023. "The Consequences of Generative AI for Democracy, Governance and War." *Survival* 65(5): 117–142. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00396338.2023.2261260>

Fontes, Catarina, Ellen Hohma, Caitlin C. Corrigan, and Christoph Lütge. 2022. "AI-powered public surveillance systems: why we (might) need them and how we want them." *Technology in Society* 71. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160791X22002780>

Funk, Allie, Adrian Shahbaz, and Kian Vesteinsson. 2023. *Freedom on the Net 2023: The Repressive Power of Artificial Intelligence*. Washington, DC: Freedom House. <https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-net/2023/repressive-power-artificial-intelligence>

Gleicher, Nathaniel. 2019. "Removing Coordinated Inauthentic Behavior in UAE, Egypt and Saudi Arabia." Meta. August 1. <https://about.fb.com/news/2019/08/cib-uae-egypt-saudi-arabia/>

Government Hacks Activists with NSO Group Zero-Click iPhone Exploits." *Citizen Lab*. August 24. <https://citizenlab.ca/research/bahrain-hacks-activists-with-nso-group-zero-click-iphone-exploits/>

Gümrükçü, Selin Bengi. 2025. "Artificial Intelligence–Based Aesthetics of Dissent in Turkey." *Public Seminar*, June 18. <https://publicseminar.org/2025/06/turkey-protesters-using-ai/>

Huntley, Shane. 2024. "TAG Bulletin: Q4 2023." *Google Threat Analysis Group*. January 19. <https://blog.google/threat-analysis-group/tag-bulletin-q4-2023/>

James, Noel. 2025. "Women This Week: Iran Using Electronic Surveillance to Enforce Veiling Laws." *Council on Foreign Relations*. March 24. <https://www.cfr.org/articles/women-week-iran-using-electronic-surveillance-enforce-veiling-laws>

JournalismAI. 2024. "Verify Media Platform." Innovation Challenge 2024. <https://www.journalismai.info/programmes/innovation/innovation-challenge-2024/verify-media-platform>

Kalluri, Pratyusha Ria, William Agnew, and Abeba Birhane. 2025. "Computer-vision research powers surveillance technology." *Nature* 643, 73–79. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-08972-6>

Keaten, Jamey and Jon Gambrell. 2025. "UN Report Warns Iran Is Stepping Up Electronic Surveillance of Women to Enforce Headscarf Laws." *Associated Press*. March 14. <https://apnews.com/article/e6d33c4f45f0181b9b-c4669aef196209>

Kerley, Beth, Carl Miller, and Fernanda Campagnucci. 2024. *Leveraging AI for Democracy: AI for Civil Society*. National Endowment for Democracy. https://www.ned.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/NED_Leveraging-AI-for-Democracy-Report_AI-for-Civil-Society.pdf

Lynch, James. 2022. "Iron Net: Digital Repression in the Middle East and North Africa." *European Council on Foreign Relations*. June 29. <https://ecfr.eu/publication/iron-net-digital-repression-in-the-middle-east-and-north-africa/>

Marcellino, William, Nathan Beauchamp-Mustafaga, Amanda Kerrigan, Lev Navarre Chao, and Jackson Smith. 2023. "The Rise of Generative AI and the Coming Era of Social Media Manipulation 3.0: Next-Generation Chinese Astroturfing and Coping with Ubiquitous AI." *RAND*. September 7. <https://www.rand.org/pubs/perspectives/PEA2679-1.html>

Marczak, Bill, John Scott-Railton, Noura Aljizawi, Siena Anstis, and Ron Deibert. 2020. "The Great iPwn: Journalists Hacked with Suspected NSO Group iMessage 'Zero-Click' Exploit." *Citizen Lab*. December 20. <https://citizenlab.ca/research/the-great-ipwn-journalists-hacked-with-suspected-nso-group-imessage-zero-click-exploit/>

Marczak, Bill, Ali Abdulemam, Noura Aljizawi, Siena Anstis, Kristin Berdan, John Scott-Railton, Ron Deibert, and Bahr Abdul Razzak. 2021. "From Pearl to Pegasus: Bahraini Government Hacks Activist Group with NSO Group Zero-Click iPhone Exploits." *Citizen Lab*. August 24. <https://citizenlab.ca/research/bahrain-hacks-activists-with-nso-group-zero-click-iphone-exploits/>

McBrien, Tyler. 2021. "The Archive as Activism: Lessons from Mnemonic and the Syrian Archive." *Exposing the Invisible*. August 10. <https://exposingtheinvisible.org/en/articles/archive-activism-mnemonic/>

Mnemonic. 2020. "Methods." March 10. <https://mnemonic.org/en/about/methods/>

NetBlocks. 2022. "Internet disrupted in Iran amid protests over death of Mahsa Amini." September 19. <https://netblocks.org/reports/internet-disrupted-in-iran-amid-protests-over-death-of-mahsa-amini-X8qVEwAD>

Open Observatory of Network Interference (OONI). 2022. "Technical multi-stakeholder report on Internet shutdowns: The case of Iran amid Autumn 2022 protests." November 29. <https://ooni.org/post/2022-iran-technical-multistakeholder-report/>

Open Observatory of Network Interference. n.d. "OONI Explorer: Egypt." <https://explorer.ooni.org/country/EG>

Open Observatory of Network Interference. n.d. "Reachability of Censorship Circumvention Tools." <https://explorer.ooni.org/circumvention>

OpenAI. 2024. Influence and Cyber Operations: An Update. October. https://cdn.openai.com/threat-intelligence-reports/influence-and-cyber-operations-an-update_October-2024.pdf

Peterson, Dahlia. 2021. "How China harnesses data fusion to make sense of surveillance data." *Brookings Institution*. September 23. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/how-china-harnesses-data-fusion-to-make-sense-of-surveillance-data/>

Presight. n.d. "Presight AI-Policing Suite." <https://www.presight.ai/news/presight-launches-groundbreaking-ai-policing-suite-at-world-police-summit-2025-to-transform-law-enforcement-operations>

Rosson, Zach, Felicia Anthonio, and Carolyn Tackett. 2023. "Weapons of Control, Shields of Impunity, Internet Shutdowns in 2022: The #KeepItOn Report." *Access Now*. February 28. <https://www.accessnow.org/internet-shutdowns-2022/>

Reuters. 2023. “CCTV Cameras Will Watch Over Egyptians in New High-Tech Capital.” January 4. <https://www.reuters.com/world/cctv-cameras-will-watch-over-egyptians-new-high-tech-capital--trfn-2023-01-04/>

Reuters. 2024. “Iran’s Supreme Leader Calls for Regulation of Cyberspace.” August 27. <https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/irans-supreme-leader-calls-regulation-cyberspace-2024-08-27/>

Reuters. 2026. “Digital blackout hits Tehran, other parts of Iran, NetBlocks says.” January 8. <https://www.reuters.com/business/media-telecom/digital-blackout-hits-tehran-other-parts-iran-netblocks-says-2026-01-08/>

Sengupta, Neha, et al. 2023. “Jais and Jais-chat: Arabic-Centric Foundation and Instruction-Tuned Open Generative Large Language Models.” *arXiv* (2308.16149). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.16149>

Shahbaz, Adrian and Allie Funk. 2019. *Freedom on the Net 2019: The Crisis of Social Media*. Washington, DC: Freedom House. <https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-net/2019/crisis-social-media>

Syrian Archive. n.d. “Methods and Tools.” <https://syrianarchive.org/en/about/methods-and-tools/>

Tech & Justice Project (Oxford). n.d. “United Arab Emirates.” *Oxford Institute of Technology and Justice*. <https://www.techandjustice.bsg.ox.ac.uk/research/united-arab-emirates>

Zhuravskaya, Ekaterina, Maria Petrova, and Ruben Enikolopov. 2020. “Political Effects of the Internet and Social Media.” *Annual Review of Economics* 12: 415–438. <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev-economics-081919-050239>